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Detecting the Variation of Flow Number (FN) Through the Durability Assessment of Asphalt Concrete (AC)

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ABSTRACT

To monitor the rutting potential of AC mixture throughout its service life, the FN plays a critical parameter which should be considered. The FN is the number of load cycles at which permanent deformation initiates in the flexible pavement and increases significantly under dynamic loading. The influence of long-term ageing and moisture damage on the FN of AC mixture were evaluated in the present durability assessment. Beam specimens of roller compacted AC mixtures were investigated for their resistance to fatigue under dynamic flexural stresses and constant strain level of 400 microstrain before and after practicing the moisture damage and long-term ageing processes. The testing of the beams for flexure was conducted at 20° C environment. It was observed that the FN increased after practicing long-term ageing by (16.6, and 66.6) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively. At the same time, it declined by (33.3, and 178) % for AC mixtures prepared with (5.3, and 4.3) % binder, respectively after practicing the moisture damage process as compared with the control mixtures. The permanent deformation of AC mixture declined after practicing the long-term ageing process by (0.8, and 12.4) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder, respectively. However, the permanent deformation of AC mixture increased after practicing the moisture damage process by (5, and 11.1) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively.

Keywords: Asphalt concrete, flow number, moisture damage, ageing, flexure, strain, binder content

INTRODUCTION

Breakah and Williams, 2015, [1] used finite element modeling and utilized the results of mechanistic tests to evaluate the moisture susceptibility of laboratory compacted AC mixtures. Dynamic modulus tests were performed on AC specimens before and after moisture conditioning. The same AC specimens were then used for FN testing. The dynamic modulus results were used as input as a finite element model and the model was validated by the results from the FN test. It was concluded that the finite element analysis exhibited that the results' variability increases with moisture conditioning.

The performance of AC mixture is influenced by ageing and exposure to moisture, and the service life of AC substantially reduces. Estimation of the moisture damage potential to AC mixture under cyclic loading was conducted by Jitsangiam et al., 2019, [2] with the aid of dynamic creep testing which provides the FN. It was revealed that FN ratio of two tested mixtures dropped below 80%. It was concluded that the dynamic creep test can be used for testing the stripping potential in AC mixtures. Xi et al., 2021, [3] examined the sensitivity to moisture of AC mixtures by implementing the FN test. AC specimens were conditioned under four conditions. FN test was conducted to assess the moisture susceptibility of AC mixtures. It was noticed that FN exhibits a gradually decreasing tendency with the rise in humidity level. FN test is a recommended way to assess the trend of permanent deformation of AC mixtures under different humidity conditions. Liu et al., 2021, [4] stated that the FN test is a simple performance test and become more widely used to assess the permanent deformation of AC mixtures.

The implemented haversine loading is more representing the loading wave of the

dynamic traffic load, while the test results usually have a good correlation with the mechanical behavior of pavement.

In addition, in the FN test, the moisture damage potential of AC can be obtained from the deformation results. Lopes et al., 2025, [5] evaluated the fatigue behavior of AC mixture through the influence of moisture-damage, and flow number tests, when subjected to different ageing protocols. The AC mixtures were subjected to short-term and long-term aging processes. A notable increase in the modulus values of AC mixtures was observed. Ma et al., 2021, [6] investigated the impact of ageing on dynamic mechanical behaviors of AC mixtures. The results show that complex modulus of AC significantly increases after ageing. An increasing trend of dynamic modulus of AC mixture as degree of aging become more serious was exhibited. Enhanced anti-deformation ability at high-temperature and weakened anti-deformation ability at low-temperature have been observed. Chen et al., 2021, [7] developed a stiffness change tendency method and determined critical fatigue failure points in the laboratory to characterize different fatigue damage stages.

The measured reduction in the stiffness of AC mixture versus loading curves were determined for a range of AC mixtures in control, moisture damaged, and aged conditions by testing with the aid of four-point bending fatigue tests. Radeef et al., 2022, [8] explored the influence of moisture damage and ageing on the mechanical properties of AC mixtures. The properties of rutting and dynamic creep were calculated to evaluate the influence of short and long-term ageing and moisture damage. The test results indicated that moisture conditioning has significantly deteriorated the mixture's resistance to permanent deformation and cracking. The

rutting resistance and modulus of the AC mixtures have declined after moisture conditioning. Sarsam, 2024, [9] detected the failure mechanism of AC mixture when sustaining environmental influence. It was observed that when 250 Microstrain was implemented, the failure mechanism occurred in three stages, while five stages of failure are observed under 400 Microstrain. However, two stages of failure could be verified under 750 Microstrain.

The aim of this investigation is to assess the behavior of AC mixtures when practicing moisture damage and long-term ageing conditions and the role of FN in distinguishing the variation in the permanent deformation of AC mixtures under such circumstances. The influence of two binder contents, and constant strain

level of 400 microstrain on the FN of AC when practicing dynamic flexural stresses at moderate temperature of 20° C will be evaluated. Beam specimens of roller compacted AC mixture will be tested in the dynamic four points bending beam fatigue test apparatus before and after practicing the moisture damage and long-term ageing. The FN of AC will be detected and its variation with the testing variables will be analyzed.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Asphalt Cement

Asphalt cement with a penetration of 43, and super-pave designation of (PG 64-16) was obtained from Al-Durah oil refinery. Physical properties of asphalt cement binder are shown in Figure 1. The testing was conducted according to ASTM, 2019, [10] procedures.

Fig. 1: Properties of Asphalt Cement.

Fine and Coarse Aggregates

The aggregates (fine and Coarse) were obtained from Al-Nibae quarry; Figure 2 illustrates their important physical

properties. The testing was conducted according to ASTM, 2019, [10] procedures.

Fig. 2: Properties of Aggregates.

Mineral Filler

The limestone dust was used as a mineral filler; it was obtained from Karbala plant. The bulk specific gravity of the filler was 2.617, while the percent finer than 75 micron was 94 %.

Combined Gradation of AC

The selected aggregates gradation in the present work is according to the SCRB, 2003, [11] requirements for dense graded binder course with 19 mm nominal

maximum size of aggregates. Figure 3 shows the investigated aggregate gradation.

Preparation of AC mixture

The AC mixture was prepared according to Marshall test procedure presented in ASTM, 2019, [10]. Specimens of 102 mm in diameter and 63.5 mm in height were prepared with various binder percentages and tested in accordance with ASTM, 2019, [10].

Fig. 3: Grain size distribution of AC mixture according to SCRB, 2003.

Preparation of Asphalt Concrete Mixture

The asphalt cement was heated to 150 °C and then mixed with the combination of

the coarse and fine aggregates and mineral filler which was heated to 160 °C. The 4.8 % asphalt cement binder was the optimum content which was obtained based on

Marshall Test trials. More details of the optimum binder requirement may be found in Sarsam, 2022, [12]. The AC mixtures were compacted in a slab mold of (300 × 400) mm while the depth of the mold was 60 mm. Laboratory roller compaction was implemented until a target bulk density was reached according to procedure details by EN12697-33, 2007, [13]. More details of the compaction process may be found in Sarsam and AL Nuaimi, 2020, [14]. Three Beam specimens of 56 mm height, 400 mm length, and 62 mm width, were obtained from each of the prepared slab sample with the aid of diamond-saw.

The total number of the prepared slab samples of AC was three, while the number of asphalt concrete beam specimens was eighteen; two beam specimens were tested for each testing temperature. The accepted standard deviation between the maximum and minimum values was 5 % and the average value of a minimum duplicate specimens was considered for the analysis for each testing temperature.

Moisture Damage Process

One portion of the prepared asphalt concrete beam specimens was subjected to laboratory moisture damage by immersion in a water bath at 25° C for 120 minutes. A vacuum of 3.74 kPa was applied for evacuation of the air in the voids of the asphalt concrete mixture for 10 minutes so that 80 % saturation of the beam specimens could be obtained. The beam Specimens were placed in a freezer at -18°C ± 1°C for a minimum of 16 hours then removed from the freezer and placed into water bath for 24± 1 hour at a 60± 1°C. Beam specimens were removed from the water bath and were placed in another

water bath at 25 ± 0.5 °C for about 2 hours, and then they were tested according to AASHTO, 2013, [15].

Long-Term Ageing Process

Another part of the asphalt concrete beam specimens practiced oxidation ageing (long-term ageing). The beam specimens were stored in an oven for (120 hours) at 85°C as recommended by AASHTO R-30, 2013, [16] procedure. Beam specimens of asphalt concrete were removed from the ageing oven and kept in the testing chamber of the dynamic testing apparatus for 120 minutes at 20°C testing temperature for the dynamic flexural fatigue test.

Testing for Fatigue life with the aid of Dynamic Flexural Bending Beam Test

The fatigue life of AC in the present work was monitored as the elapsed time consumed for the start point of loading to the initiation of failure signs. It may also be monitored through the number of loading cycles which cause failure or cause a reduction in the flexural stiffness to 50 % of its original value. The four-point dynamic flexural bending beam test was conducted according to AASHTO T321, 2010, [17]. Figure 4 exhibits the test setup. The beam specimens were stored in the testing chamber for three hours at the specific testing temperature before practicing the dynamic flexural stresses. The influence of three binder percentages (4.3, 4.8, and 5.3) % on the FN of AC was detected at 20 °C environments in terms of the changes in FM, and flexural permanent microstrain. A similar testing procedure using dynamic stress was adopted by Chen et al., 2021, [7].

Fig. 4: Four-point flexural bending beam test setup.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 5 exhibits the influence of long-term ageing on the FN of AC mixture when tested under constant microstrain level of 400. It can be observed that the ageing process causes decline in the permanent deformation of AC, while it increases the FN and the fatigue life of AC. The FN increased after practicing long-term ageing by (16.6, and 66.6) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively as compared with the control mixtures. However, the fatigue life of AC mixtures increased by (316, and 600) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively as compared with the control mixtures. Such

behavior could be attributed to stiffening of the binder during the ageing process. Higher binder content exhibits higher FN and higher fatigue life of AC mixtures. The permanent deformation of AC mixture declined after practicing the long-term ageing process by (0.8, and 12.4) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively. The stiffening of the binder through the ageing process increases its viscosity, adhesion to aggregates, and limits the cohesion between the coated aggregates with binder which prolongs the fatigue life and increases the FN. Lopes et al., 2025, [5]; and Ma et al., 2021, [6] reported similar behavior.

Fig. 5: Influence of Long-Term Ageing on the FN.

Figure 6 exhibits the influence of moisture damage on the FN of AC mixture when tested under constant microstrain level of 400. It can be detected that the FN declined after practicing the moisture damage by (33.3, and 178) % for AC mixtures prepared with (5.3, and 4.3) % binder respectively as compared with the control mixtures.

However, the fatigue life of AC mixtures declined by (25, and 20) % for AC mixtures prepared with (5.3, and 4.3) % binder respectively as compared with the control mixtures. On the other hand, higher binder content shows higher FN of AC mixture regardless of the moisture damage process. Similar findings were reported by

Breakah and Williams, 2015, [1]. The permanent deformation of AC mixture increased after practicing the moisture damage process by (5, and 11.1) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively.

The stripping action of the binder from the aggregates due to long exposure to immersion in water causes reduction in the stiffness of AC mixture and negatively influences the adhesion of the binder to aggregates and cohesion between aggregates particles. Initiation of distress of AC mixture starts earlier and the FN exhibits lower values as compared with that of the control mixtures.

Fig. 6: Influence of moisture damage on the FN.

Figure 7 summarizes the influence of durability testing conditions on the FN of AC. It shows that the FN increases after practicing the long-term ageing process as

the scatter of data is above the 45° line, while FN declines after practicing the moisture damage process as the scatter of data is below the 45° line.

Fig. 7: Influence of durability testing conditions on FN of AC mixtures.

CONCLUSIONS

The limitations of materials and the implemented testing program can address the following remarks.

- The FN increased after practicing long-term ageing by (16.6, and 66.6) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively as compared with the control mixtures.
- The FN declined after practicing the moisture damage by (33.3, and 178) % for AC mixtures prepared with (5.3, and 4.3) % binder respectively as compared with the control mixtures.
- The fatigue life of AC mixtures increased by (316, and 600) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively after practicing long-term ageing process as compared with the control mixtures.
- The fatigue life of AC mixtures declined by (25, and 20) % for AC mixtures prepared with (5.3, and 4.3) % binder respectively after practicing moisture damage as compared with the control mixtures.
- The permanent deformation of AC mixture declined after practicing the

long-term ageing process by (0.8, and 12.4) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively.

- The permanent deformation of AC mixture increased after practicing the moisture damage process by (5, and 11.1) % for AC mixtures prepared with (4.3, and 4.8) % binder respectively.

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